

NONLOCAL ELLIPTIC VARIATIONAL-HEMIVARIATIONAL INEQUALITIES

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We examine the existence of a weak solution to a class of variational-hemivariational inequalities governed by a fractional Laplace operator. Moreover, an existence result is proved for a bilateral obstacle problem for a nonlocal hemivariational inequality. Our approach is based on a surjectivity result for pseudomonotone mappings, properties of Clarke's subgradient, and the Moreau–Yosida approximation.

1. Introduction and motivation

Let $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, $N > 2\alpha$, and Ω be a bounded, open subset of \mathbb{R}^N with Lipschitz boundary $\partial\Omega$. In this paper, given $f: \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $j: \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, and $\Phi: E_\alpha \rightarrow \bar{\mathbb{R}} := \mathbb{R} \cup \{+\infty\}$, we consider the following nonlocal variational-hemivariational inequality of elliptic type:

$$(1) \quad \begin{cases} (-\Delta)^\alpha u + \partial J(u) + \partial_c \Phi(u) \ni f & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = 0 & \text{in } \Omega^c := \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega, \end{cases}$$

where the operator $(-\Delta)^\alpha$ is the well-known nonlocal Laplace operator defined for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^N$ by

$$-(\Delta)^\alpha u(x) := \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \frac{u(x+y) + u(x-y) - 2u(x)}{|y|^{N+2\alpha}} dy,$$

and $\partial J(\cdot)$ stands for the generalized Clarke subdifferential operator of a locally Lipschitz functional J (see hypothesis $H(j)$ below):

$$(2) \quad J(v) := \int_{\Omega} j(x, v(x)) dx, \quad \text{for all } v \in L^p(\Omega),$$

and $\partial_c \Phi(\cdot)$ denotes the convex subdifferential operator of a convex functional Φ (see hypothesis $H(\Phi)$).

Let $H^\alpha(\mathbb{R}^N)$ be the usual fractional Sobolev space. Using the fact that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} v(x) (-\Delta)^s u(x) dx = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \frac{(u(x) - u(y))(v(x) - v(y))}{|x - y|^{N+2\alpha}} dy dx$$

for all $v \in H^\alpha(\mathbb{R}^N)$ with $v = 0$ in Ω^c , along with [7], we give the definition of a weak solution to (1).

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Definition 1. A function $u: \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called to be a weak solution to (1), if there exist $\xi \in \partial J(u)$ and $\eta \in \partial_c \Phi(u)$ such that

$$\frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \frac{(u(x) - u(y))(v(x) - v(y))}{|x - y|^{N+2\alpha}} dy dx + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} (\xi(x) + \eta(x))v(x) dx = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} f(x)v(x) dx$$

for all $v \in H^\alpha(\mathbb{R}^N)$ with $v = 0$ in Ω^c .

Partial differential equations involving nonlocal operators have recently attracted a lot of attention, because nonlocal operators can describe accurately many complex systems in our real life, for example: anomalous diffusion phenomenon, dynamical networks behaviors, and geophysical flows, etc.; see [15; 2; 4; 5; 16; 22]. On the other hand, the theory of hemivariational inequalities as a generalization of variational inequalities is based on the notion of the Clarke subgradient defined for locally Lipschitz functions. The theory started with the works of Panagiotopoulos, see [17; 18], and has been substantially developed during the last thirty years. The mathematical results on hemivariational and variational-hemivariational inequalities have found numerous applications to mechanics, physics, and engineering; see [6; 9; 8; 10; 14; 11; 13; 12; 25; 26].

Quite recently, the study of hemivariational inequalities involving nonlocal operators has drawn a wide range of interest, for instance, Teng [23] and Xi, Huang, and Zhou [24] applied the nonsmooth critical theory and a nonsmooth version of the three-critical-points theorem to prove the multiplicity of weak solutions to nonlocal elliptic hemivariational inequalities. It is worth mentioning that in certain situations, the formulated problems do not have variational structure. This results in that the nonsmooth critical point theory and the nonsmooth variational approaches cannot be carried out. Motivated by this reason, more recently, Liu and Tan [7] have considered the nonlocal hemivariational inequality (1) with $\Phi = 0$ by using a surjectivity result for pseudomonotone and coercive operators. Unfortunately, the main results of Liu and Tan [7] cannot be applied to problems which are controlled by a convex subdifferential operator, for example, a bilateral obstacle problem for nonlocal hemivariational inequality:

$$(3) \quad \begin{cases} u \in K(\pi, \tau), \\ (-\Delta)^\alpha u + \partial J(u) \ni f & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = 0 & \text{in } \Omega^c, \end{cases}$$

where the set $K(\pi, \tau)$ is defined by

$$K(\pi, \tau) := \{u \in E_\alpha \mid \pi(x) \leq u(x) \leq \tau(x) \text{ for a.e. } x \in \Omega\},$$

with $\pi, \tau \in E_\alpha$ and $\pi(x) \leq \tau(x)$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$. In fact, (3) can be reformulated as (1) with $\Phi = I_{K(\pi, \tau)}$, where $I_{K(\pi, \tau)}$ stands for the indicator function of $K(\pi, \tau)$, i.e.,

$$I_{K(\pi, \tau)}(u) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } u \in K(\pi, \tau), \\ +\infty & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The aim of this paper is to fill the gap and explore the existence of weak solutions for (1).

2. Existence of solutions

We will first recall basic notation, definitions, and some auxiliary results from nonlocal fractional operators and nonlinear analysis.

Definition 2. Let $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and Ω be a bounded, open subset of \mathbb{R}^N with Lipschitz boundary and $N > 2\alpha$. The space E_α defined by

$$E_\alpha = \left\{ u \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^N) \mid \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{N+2\alpha}} dx dy < +\infty \text{ and } u \equiv 0 \text{ in } \Omega^c \right\}$$

is called the fractional α -Sobolev space.

Remark 3. It is obvious that $C_0^2(\Omega) \subseteq E_\alpha \subseteq L^2(\Omega)$ for all $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ with $N > 2\alpha$; see, e.g., [20]. Hence, we know that the fractional α -Sobolev space is nonempty and dense in $L^2(\Omega)$ for all $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ with $N > 2\alpha$.

The following lemma, whose proof can be found in [15; 1; 19; 21], delivers some important properties of the fractional α -Sobolev space E_α .

Lemma 4. Let $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, Ω be a bounded, open subset of \mathbb{R}^N with Lipschitz boundary, $N > 2\alpha$, and $2^* = 2N/(N - 2\alpha)$. Then we have:

(i) E_α is a Hilbert space with the inner product

$$\langle u, v \rangle_{E_\alpha} := \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \frac{(u(x) - u(y))(v(x) - v(y))}{|x - y|^{N+2\alpha}} dx dy$$

for all $u, v \in E_\alpha$ and the associated (Gagliardo) norm denoted by $\|\cdot\|_{E_\alpha}$.

(ii) If $p \in [1, 2^*]$, then there exists a positive constant $c(p)$ such that

$$\|u\|_{L^p(\mathbb{R}^N)} \leq c(p) \|u\|_{E_\alpha} \quad \text{for all } u \in E_\alpha.$$

(iii) The embedding from E_α to $L^p(\mathbb{R}^N)$ is compact for any $p \in [1, 2^*]$.

Lemma 5. Let X be a Banach space and $\varphi: X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be a proper, convex, and lower semicontinuous function. Then, for $\varepsilon > 0$, the Moreau–Yosida approximation $\varphi_\varepsilon: X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ of φ defined by

$$\varphi_\varepsilon(u) = \inf_{v \in X} \left(\frac{\|u - v\|_X^2}{2\varepsilon} + \varphi(v) \right)$$

for all $u \in X$, satisfies the following properties:

(i) φ_ε is convex, lower semicontinuous, and Gâteaux differentiable.

(ii) The differential operator $\varphi'_\varepsilon: X \rightarrow X^*$ is bounded, monotone, and demicontinuous.

(iii) If $u_\varepsilon \rightarrow u$ weakly in X , then we have

$$\limsup_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \varphi_\varepsilon(v) \leq \varphi(v) \quad \text{for all } v \in X,$$

$$\varphi(u) \leq \liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \varphi_\varepsilon(u_\varepsilon)$$

as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$.

For the discussion below, we impose the following hypotheses on the data to (1):

H(j): $j: \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is such that:

(i) $x \mapsto j(x, s)$ is measurable on Ω for all $r \in \mathbb{R}$ and $x \mapsto j(x, 0)$ belongs to $L^1(\Omega)$.

- (ii) $s \mapsto j(x, s)$ is locally Lipschitz for a.e. $x \in \Omega$.
 (iii) There exist $p \geq 1$, $c > 0$, and $b \in L^{p/(p-1)}(\Omega)$ such that

$$|\xi| \leq b(x) + c |s|^{p-1} \quad \text{for all } \xi \in \partial j(x, s) \text{ and a.e. } x \in \Omega.$$

$H(\Phi)$: $\Phi: E_\alpha \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ is a proper, convex, and lower semicontinuous functional.

Remark 6. From hypothesis $H(j)$ and [7, Lemma 2.6], we can see that the functional J defined by (2) satisfies the following properties:

- (i) J is locally Lipschitz.
 (ii) There exists a positive constant c_1 such that

$$\|\xi\|_{L^{p'}(\Omega)} \leq c_1 (1 + \|u\|_{L^p(\Omega)}^{p-1}) \quad \text{for all } \xi \in \partial(J|_{L^p(\Omega)})(u) \text{ and } u \in L^p(\Omega),$$

where $1/p + 1/p' = 1$.

We now give the main result of the paper concerning the existence of a solution to (1) in the sense of Definition 1.

Theorem 7. Assume that $H(j)$ and $H(\Phi)$ hold with $1 \leq p < 2$ or $p = 2$ such that $2c_1c(p)^p < 1$ (see Lemma 4 and Remark 6). Then, (1) admits a solution in the sense of Definition 1.

Proof. First, for $\varepsilon > 0$, we consider the auxiliary problem

$$(4) \quad (-\Delta)^\alpha u_\varepsilon + \partial J(u_\varepsilon) + \Phi'_\varepsilon(u_\varepsilon) \ni f,$$

where $\Phi_\varepsilon: E_\alpha \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is the Moreau–Yosida approximation of Φ defined by

$$\Phi_\varepsilon(u) := \inf_{v \in E_\alpha} \left(\frac{\|u - v\|_{E_\alpha}^2}{2\varepsilon} + \Phi(v) \right)$$

for all $u \in E_\alpha$.

Now, we shall prove the existence of a solution to (4). From [7, Proposition 3.2], we know that the mapping $E_\alpha \ni u \mapsto (-\Delta)^\alpha u + \partial J(u) \subset E_\alpha^*$ is pseudomonotone and has nonempty, convex, and weak-compact values. Recall that the operator $\Phi'_\varepsilon: E_\alpha \rightarrow E_\alpha^*$ is bounded, demicontinuous, and monotone; so, we use [14, Theorem 3.69] to get that Φ'_ε is pseudomonotone as well. Hence, we deduce that $E_\alpha \ni u \mapsto (-\Delta)^\alpha u + \partial J(u) + \Phi'_\varepsilon(u) \subset E_\alpha^*$ is pseudomonotone.

Next, we will verify that $E_\alpha \ni u \mapsto (-\Delta)^\alpha u + \partial J(u) + \Phi'_\varepsilon(u) \subset E_\alpha^*$ is coercive. For any $\xi \in \partial J(u)$, we calculate, see [7, Lemma 3.1] and Remark 6,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u + \xi + \Phi'_\varepsilon(u), u \rangle_{E_\alpha} &\geq \frac{1}{2} \|u\|_{E_\alpha}^2 - \|\xi\|_{L^{p'}(\Omega)} \|u\|_{L^p(\Omega)} + \langle \Phi'_\varepsilon(0), u \rangle_{E_\alpha} + \langle \Phi'_\varepsilon(u) - \Phi'_\varepsilon(0), u \rangle_{E_\alpha} \\ &\geq \frac{1}{2} \|u\|_{E_\alpha}^2 - c_1 \|u\|_{L^p(\Omega)} - c_1 \|u\|_{L^p(\Omega)}^p - \|\Phi'_\varepsilon(0)\|_{E_\alpha^*} \|u\|_{E_\alpha} \\ &\geq \frac{1}{2} \|u\|_{E_\alpha}^2 - c_1 c(p) \|u\|_{E_\alpha} - c_1 c(p)^p \|u\|_{E_\alpha}^p - \|\Phi'_\varepsilon(0)\|_{E_\alpha^*} \|u\|_{E_\alpha} \end{aligned}$$

for all $u \in E_\alpha$. The assumption, $1 \leq p < 2$ or $p = 2$ with $2c_1c(p)^p < 1$, reveals that $E_\alpha \ni u \mapsto (-\Delta)^\alpha u + \partial J(u) + \Phi'_\varepsilon(u) \subset E_\alpha^*$ is coercive.

Therefore, we apply the surjectivity result in [14, Theorem 3.74] to infer that there exists $u_\varepsilon \in E_\alpha$ such that (4) holds.

Next, we assert that the sequence $\{u_\varepsilon\}_\varepsilon$ is bounded in E_α . Here, we just verify the case when $1 \leq p < 2$, as the proof of the case when $p = 2$ is similar. Let $v \in E_\alpha$. Multiplying (4) by $v - u_\varepsilon$, one has

$$\langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u_\varepsilon + \xi_\varepsilon + \Phi'_\varepsilon(u_\varepsilon), v - u_\varepsilon \rangle_{E_\alpha} = \langle f, v - u_\varepsilon \rangle_{E_\alpha},$$

where $\xi_\varepsilon \in \partial J(u_\varepsilon)$. The convexity of Φ_ε implies

$$(5) \quad \langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u_\varepsilon + \xi_\varepsilon, v - u_\varepsilon \rangle_{E_\alpha} + \Phi_\varepsilon(v) - \Phi_\varepsilon(u_\varepsilon) \geq \langle f, v - u_\varepsilon \rangle_{E_\alpha}.$$

Hence, we have

$$\langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u_\varepsilon + \xi_\varepsilon, u_\varepsilon \rangle_{E_\alpha} + \Phi_\varepsilon(u_\varepsilon) \leq \langle f, u_\varepsilon - v \rangle_{E_\alpha} + \Phi_\varepsilon(v) + \langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u_\varepsilon + \xi_\varepsilon, v \rangle_{E_\alpha}.$$

Since Φ_ε is a proper, convex, and lower semicontinuous functional, it is bounded from below by an affine function; and hence, there are two constants $k_1, k_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$\Phi_\varepsilon(u) \geq k_1 \|u\|_{E_\alpha} + k_2$$

for all $u \in E_\alpha$. This implies

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} \|u_\varepsilon\|_{E_\alpha}^2 - c_1 \|u_\varepsilon\|_{L^p(\Omega)} - c_1 \|u_\varepsilon\|_{L^p(\Omega)}^p + k_1 \|u_\varepsilon\|_{E_\alpha} + k_2 \\ \leq \|f\|_{E_\alpha^*} (\|u_\varepsilon\|_{E_\alpha} + \|v\|_{E_\alpha}) + \|(-\Delta)^\alpha u_\varepsilon\|_{E_\alpha^*} \|v\|_{E_\alpha} + \|\xi_\varepsilon\|_{L^{p'}(\Omega)} \|v\|_{L^p(\Omega)} + \Phi_\varepsilon(v). \end{aligned}$$

We use Young's inequality with $\delta > 0$ to obtain the inequalities

$$\begin{aligned} c_1 c(p)^p \|u\|_{E_\alpha}^p &\leq \delta \|u\|_{E_\alpha}^2 + \frac{2-p}{2} \left[\left(\sqrt{\frac{p}{2\delta}} \right)^p c_1 c(p)^p \right]^{2/(2-p)}, \\ (c_1 c(p) + |k_1|) \|u\|_{E_\alpha} &\leq \delta \|u\|_{E_\alpha}^2 + \frac{1}{4\delta} (c_1 c(p) + |k_1|)^2, \\ \|f\|_{E_\alpha} \|u\|_{E_\alpha} &\leq \delta \|u\|_{E_\alpha}^2 + \frac{1}{4\delta} \|f\|_{E_\alpha^*}^2, \\ c_1 c(p)^p \|u\|_{E_\alpha}^{p-1} \|v\|_{E_\alpha} &\leq \frac{3-p}{2} \left[\left(\sqrt{\frac{p-1}{2\delta}} \right)^{p-1} c_1 c(p)^p \|v\|_{E_\alpha} \right]^{2/(3-p)} + \delta \|u\|_{E_\alpha}^p, \end{aligned}$$

which when combined with Lemma 4 yields

$$\frac{1}{2} (1 - 10\delta) \|u_\varepsilon\|_{E_\alpha}^2 \leq m_0 (1 + \|v\|_{E_\alpha}^2 + \|v\|_{E_\alpha}^{2/(3-p)}) + \Phi_\varepsilon(v),$$

where $m_0 > 0$ is independent of ε . Now, we choose $\delta < \frac{1}{10}$ and $v \in \text{dom } \Phi$ to conclude that

$$\|u_\varepsilon\|_{E_\alpha} \leq m_1,$$

where $m_1 > 0$ is independent of ε . So, $\{u_\varepsilon\}$ is bounded in E_α .

Subsequently, passing to a subsequence if necessary, we may assume that $u_\varepsilon \rightharpoonup u$ weakly in E_α . Inserting $v = u$ in (5) and passing to the limit in the resulting inequality, we have by Lemma 5(iii)

$$\limsup_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u_\varepsilon + \xi_\varepsilon, u_\varepsilon - u \rangle_{E_\alpha} \leq \limsup_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \Phi_\varepsilon(u) - \liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \Phi_\varepsilon(u_\varepsilon) \leq 0.$$

Using [3, Theorem 2.2], we obtain $\partial(J|_{E_\alpha})(u) \subset \partial(J|_{L^p(\Omega)})(u)$ for all $u \in E_\alpha$. Hence, we deduce that $\langle \xi, v \rangle_{E_\alpha} \leq \|\xi\|_{L^{p'}(\Omega)} \|v\|_{L^p(\Omega)}$ for all $\xi \in \partial J(u)$. Therefore, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \limsup_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u_\varepsilon, u_\varepsilon - u \rangle_{E_\alpha} - \liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \|\xi_\varepsilon\|_{L^{p'}(\Omega)} \|u_\varepsilon - u\|_{L^p(\Omega)} \\ \leq \liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \langle \xi_\varepsilon, u_\varepsilon - u \rangle_{E_\alpha} + \limsup_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u_\varepsilon, u_\varepsilon - u \rangle_{E_\alpha} \\ \leq \limsup_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u_\varepsilon + \xi_\varepsilon, u_\varepsilon - u \rangle \leq 0. \end{aligned}$$

The compact embedding result, see Lemma 4(iii), reveals that $u_\varepsilon \rightarrow u$ in $L^p(\Omega)$. Therefore, we get

$$\limsup_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u_\varepsilon, u_\varepsilon - u \rangle_{E_\alpha} \leq 0.$$

Using the above inequality and the strong monotonicity of $(-\Delta)^\alpha$, one has

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq \liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{2} \|u - u_\varepsilon\|_{E_\alpha}^2 &\leq \limsup_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{2} \|u - u_\varepsilon\|_{E_\alpha}^2 \\ &\leq \limsup_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u_\varepsilon - (-\Delta)^\alpha u, u_\varepsilon - v \rangle_{E_\alpha} \leq 0. \end{aligned}$$

So, we have $u_\varepsilon \rightarrow u$ in E_α as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. As before, we can show that $\{\xi_\varepsilon\}_\varepsilon \subset E_\alpha^*$ is bounded, and we may assume that $\xi_\varepsilon \rightarrow \xi$ weakly in E_α^* . Note that the graph of $\partial(J|_{E_\alpha})$ is strongly-weakly upper semicontinuous; hence, we conclude that $\xi \in \partial J(u)$.

Moreover, recall that $(-\Delta)^\alpha: E_\alpha \rightarrow E_\alpha^*$ is linear, bounded, and strongly monotone, see [7, Lemma 3.1], so it is pseudomonotone. This implies

$$\liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u_\varepsilon, u_\varepsilon - v \rangle_{E_\alpha} \geq \langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u, u - v \rangle_{E_\alpha}$$

for all $v \in E_\alpha$. We are now in a position to take the limit of (5) to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \xi, v - u \rangle_{E_\alpha} + \Phi(v) - \Phi(u) - \langle f, v - u \rangle_{E_\alpha} \\ \geq \limsup_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \langle \xi_\varepsilon, v - u_\varepsilon \rangle_{E_\alpha} + \limsup_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \Phi_\varepsilon(v) - \liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \Phi_\varepsilon(u_\varepsilon) - \liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \langle f, v - u_\varepsilon \rangle_{E_\alpha} \\ \geq \limsup_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u_\varepsilon, u_\varepsilon - v \rangle_{E_\alpha} \geq \liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u_\varepsilon, u_\varepsilon - v \rangle_{E_\alpha} \\ \geq \langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u, u - v \rangle_{E_\alpha} \end{aligned}$$

for all $v \in E_\alpha$. Hence

$$\langle (-\Delta)^\alpha u + \xi, v - u \rangle_{E_\alpha} + \Phi(v) - \Phi(u) \geq \langle f, v - u \rangle_{E_\alpha},$$

with $\xi \in \partial J(u)$ for all $v \in E_\alpha$. This means that there exists $\eta \in \partial_c \Phi(u)$ such that

$$(-\Delta)^\alpha u + \xi + \eta \ni f \quad \text{in } E_\alpha^*.$$

Therefore, (1) has at least one weak solution in the sense of Definition 1. □

For $\Phi = 0$, we deduce the following result.

Corollary 8. Assume that $H(j)$ holds with $1 \leq p < 2$ or $p = 2$ such that $2c_1c(p)^p < 1$. Then, the problem

$$\begin{cases} (-\Delta)^\alpha u + \partial J(u) \ni f & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = 0 & \text{in } \Omega^c := \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega \end{cases}$$

admits a weak solution.

In fact, this result has been obtained recently by Liu and Tan in [7].

Finally, we prove the existence of a solution to the bilateral obstacle problem for the nonlocal hemivariational inequality (1).

Corollary 9. Assume that $H(j)$ holds with $1 \leq p < 2$ or $p = 2$ such that $2c_1c(p)^p < 1$. Then, (3) has at least one weak solution.

Proof. We define the functional $\Phi: E_\alpha \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ by $\Phi(u) = I_{K(\pi, \tau)}(u)$ for all $u \in E_\alpha$. It is obvious that Φ satisfies hypothesis $H(\Phi)$. Therefore, we apply Theorem 7 to obtain the result. \square

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